

**Collaboration and Symbiosis as Measures for Quality Control on Stage: A
Performance Review of Toni Duruaku's *Silhouettes***

Kelechi Stellamaris Ogbonna
Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri

Abstract

Drama and theatre are paradigms for cultural preservation and orientation as well as a vehicle through which positive changes are initiated. Through drama, the words of the characters and the thought of the playwright are brought before a viewing audience. Drama contains ingredients that could teach, orientate and vivify contorted images in order to correct misconceptions. That is why the dramatist writes from his environment and serves as a visionary for his society, but the artist who writes to push forward foreign cultures alienates the youths from the rich culture of the people. Hence when African dramatic literature is devoid of African cultural experience, the resultant effect is chaos. It is therefore germane to appreciate that dramatic performance, an offshoot of dramatic literature, is a collaborative art that merges the work of the dramatist and the collaborative contributions of all the arts of the theatre. Hence this study through a performance analysis of *Silhouettes*, examines the conflicts, thoughts and cultural contents of Duruaku's play as a model for political change, peaceful coexistence and nation building. The paper also examines the place of the Theatre Director in the creative enterprise as a catalyst in cultural re-orientation through stage performances. The researcher concludes that themed productions are veritable tools in the re-enforcement and effective communication of the playwright's message as interpreted by the director and her/his crew.

Key Words: Collaboration, Drama, Theatre, Performance, Culture

Résumé

L'art dramatique et le théâtre servent d'outils pour la préservation et l'orientation culturelles ainsi que de véhicule à travers lequel des changements positifs sont initiés. À travers le théâtre, les mots des personnages et la pensée du dramaturge sont portés devant un auditoire. L'art dramatique contient des éléments qui pourraient enseigner, orienter et vivifier des images déformées afin de corriger les idées fausses. C'est pourquoi le dramaturge écrit à partir de son environnement et sert de visionnaire pour sa société, mais l'artiste qui écrit pour faire avancer les cultures étrangères coupe les jeunes de la culture riche de leur peuple. Par conséquent, lorsque la littérature dramatique africaine est dépourvue d'expérience culturelle africaine, l'effet qui en résulte est le chaos. Il est donc pertinent d'apprécier le fait que la performance dramatique, qui est une émanation de la littérature dramatique, est un art collaboratif qui fusionne le travail du dramaturge et les contributions collaboratives de tous les arts du théâtre. Ainsi, à travers une analyse pratique de *Silhouettes*, la présente étude examine les conflits, les pensées et les contenus culturels de la pièce de Duruaku comme un modèle pour le changement politique, la coexistence pacifique et la construction de la

nation. L'article examine également la place du directeur de théâtre dans l'entreprise créative en tant que catalyseur dans la réorientation culturelle à travers des représentations théâtrales. Le chercheur conclut que les productions thématiques sont de véritables outils de renforcement et de communication efficace du message du dramaturge tel qu'interprété par le réalisateur et son équipe.

Mots-clés: Collaboration, drame, théâtre, performance, culture

Introduction

Drama and theatre are paradigms for cultural preservation and orientation as well as the vehicle through which positive changes are initiated. Through drama, the words of the characters and the thought of the playwright are brought before a viewing audience. Drama contains ingredients that could teach, orient and vivify images in order to correct misconceptions. That is why the dramatist writes from the environment and serves as a visionary for the society. But the artist who writes to push forward or promote foreign cultures at the expense of the local culture alienates the youths from the rich culture of their people. Hence when African dramatic literature is devoid of African cultural experiences, the resultant effect is chaotic. It is therefore germane to appreciate that dramatic performance, an offshoot of dramatic literature, is a collaborative art that merges the work of the dramatist and the collaborative contributions of all the arts of the theatre. Drama and theatre are channels through which the public can be sensitized towards positive socio-political, economic and cultural change. For it was through the instrumentation of dramatic art that the colonial masters infiltrated the hearts of the colonized while the missionaries used the same medium to affect their converts especially in schools and churches. Suffice it then to say that drama and theatre are potent instruments for strategizing, creating awareness, propaganda and campaign as well as catalyst for change and lobbying. Hence Ahmed Yerima affirms that:

The artist grows within the society, and the individual takes from society, and creates stories which he returns to society as dialectical materials for the presentation of a refraction of the realistic challenges of society, and the presentation of the alternative society to correct the ills of the society. (2013, p. 18)

It was on that premise that Zulu Sofola acknowledges art as “a creative experience which is the only human experience that is nearest to God, because it is in that experience that man shares very clearly in the most enduring and significant attributes of the Supreme Deity” (1994, p.2). Also Oscar Brockett records that art is defined as “the systematic application of knowledge or skill to achieve a desired result... art is an aid in understanding the world (1974, pp. 6 - 7). The artist is therefore endowed with a ‘super’ imagination to create, to foresee, and transform his environment because “art is...the medium through which the soul of man reaches out beyond itself to transform and make intelligible the proddings within the inner recesses for the ultimate truth...” (Sofola, 1994, p.2). Therefore, the artist could be the playwright who writes from his imagination and experiences in order to comment on his environment; the director who picks up the playwright’s images and idioms in order to

interpret, analyze, and orchestrate it into visual images and auditory sounds; the scenographer who brings to life the playwright's chosen locale and all the visual effects therein; the light designer who illuminates the play into reality; the costume and makeup designer who clothes the characters into recognizable men and women of the society; or the property master who makes sure that a king carries his staff on stage. Also, on the conception of drama as vehicle through which the society can recognize itself, Krama warns that "most playwrights or dramatists have induced the loathing of traditional values and influenced the choice of western way of life. The effect of this has led to the breakdown of traditional ties and values" (2007, p. 33), and the acceptance of strange ideas and uncommon vices into African environment.

Thus, *Silhouettes* by Toni Duruaku contains African socio-cultural and political experiences, and the raw ingredients to address socio-cultural, political, religious, and leadership questions within the micro society for which the performance is scheduled. The play text of Duruaku's *Silhouettes* is a guide manual for the production because "a script offers only a suggestion of what should or did happen...Plays are written to be performed and are not complete until they are filled out by actors, costumes and scenic background" (Brockett, 1974, p. 6). Ipso facto, quality and thematic performances put on stage for sustainable development and nation building are not the single effort of the playwright, the stage director or the actor, but the collaborative work of all the arts and/or artists of the theatre which includes the playwright, the director, actors, the light designer, choreographer, scene designer, costume and makeup designer. Because theatre is a symbiotic art, the symbiosis helps to improve the quality of work, creativity, judgment and prominence given to issues, and arguments in the world of play. The issues and agitations in the world of play are life-like and are qualitatively assured when more than three or four theatre professionals prune, organize, direct and choreograph such a performance for effective impact.

The thrust of this paper is the stage performance of Toni Duruaku's *Silhouettes* as directed by Kelechi Stellamaris Ogbonna for Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education's Golden Jubilee Celebration/Convocation in 2013. The director had to merge directing theories, organize workshops, re-write scenes, and collaborate with all the branches of theatre design to ensure that the performance reflected the theme of the Golden Jubilee anniversary and burning issues within and outside the college. Hence this study through a performance analysis of *Silhouettes*, examines the conflicts, thoughts and cultural contents of Duruaku's play under review here as a model for political change, peaceful coexistence and nation building. The paper also examines the place of the Director in the creative enterprise as well as her/his role as catalyst in cultural re-orientation through stage performances. The researcher argues that thematic productions are veritable tools for good governance and national development.

The Concept of Collaborative Art

The artist is described by Sofola (1994) as "a Seer, a Visioner, a Thinker, a Creator, the Conscience of the society, a Gadfly, a Prophet, a Town Crier, a Teacher, and a Revealer

of the Divine Mind” (p. 2). The primary concern of the artist is to create from his society for the society and for himself. He or she interrogates situations that are life-like and, as a secondary creator, signals direction towards change, suggests ideas and remedy to existing problems. Drama and theatre become a template to handle or resolve life-like conflicts since in its presentations, it burlesques with life-like situations. So when one picks up a literary drama, in it are dilemmas of the people, visions for the people, prophecies, and revelations from the ‘creative force’, “as a suggestive blue print for the society” (Sofola, 1994, p. 3). Hence drama performed on stage begins with the playwright’s idea or the ‘improvization’/actor because “the actor and the playwright are by necessity complementary, since each ultimately needs the other for the completion of his art” (Brockett, 1974, p. 4). Though the actor may perform his art by improvising his speech and action but for a serious drama/performance, it must “be organized so as to tell a story, to reveal a character, or to illustrate an idea...there is a corresponding need for greater ability to interweave story, character and ideas (Brockett, 1974, p. 4). However, it is actually the actor that confronts the audience with the playwright’s message. Again, it is through the literary drama that a glimpse of the theatre of the past is made clearer; it unveils theatrical elements and gives direction to other arts. Brockett emphasizes that,

the playwright forms a bridge between our own values and those of the past...but these artists also need the help of a director, designer, musicians and dancers...for someone must mediate the differences of opinion which arise as to positions on stage, correct line readings or interpretations of meaning (1994, p. 6).

This is why the script must be understood by the director and a team of artist(es) who refine the work of art for its perception and expression.

In the success of any theatrical performance, and for a better expression of that performance, a good director is responsible or otherwise. He/she must “decide how the script is to be interpreted, and must coordinate the efforts of all the other theatre artists into a unified performance” (Brockett: 1974, p. 363). The director ensures that the contributing arts of the theatre are effective in discharging their duties. That takes effect from the moment a script is chosen and has been interpreted and analyzed. With a cast and crew, the director “meets with the designers and discusses his approach to the play with them” (Brockett, 1974, p. 367). Therefore, effective collaboration in the performance of *Silhouettes* means that every artist worked towards the director’s metaphor in affirmation of Brockett’s position that “they may not have arrived at the same interpretation as the director, however, and the first task for all is to reach a general agreement about the basic treatment of the script” (p. 367). Yet each art contributes within the limitations and interpretation of the script as conceived by the play director.

Collaboration and Symbiosis in the Theatre

Since *Silhouettes* was chosen by the Golden Jubilee Committee to commemorate fifty years anniversary of Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education's jubilee celebration, the director of the play carefully read the play several times to arrive at the following:

1. That the play will pass through a script/performance workshop with cast and crew in participation
2. That the theme of the Golden jubilee: the theme of **Celebration** will reflect in the performance
3. That the director will have to carry out a research on the play
4. That the play's budget be adjusted to include the additional scenes.
5. That the director will have individual sessions with the playwright, the designers, the theatre managers and the actors.

This was done to facilitate effective collaboration with all the arts of the theatre during the processes of production. The *Silhouettes* was auditioned and cast after which a three-day workshop with all cast and crew took place. Hence, using the means available to the director, the production of *Silhouettes* was conceived within the artistic and managerial professionals as conceptualized and illustrated below:

The Director

The above diagram shows the relationship between the arts of the theatre as employed in the production of *Silhouettes*. The Managerial professionals are majorly concerned with the “administration of the personnel, the maintenance of the theatre building and the funding of productions” (Bell-Gam, 2007, p. 74); while the artistic professionals include “the artistic director, the assistant artistic director, the stage manager, the actors, the actresses, and the prompter. These professionals perform specific artistic functions, which collectively make up a complete theatre” (Bell-Gam, 2007, p. 74), put together with the theatre design of which the costumer, makeup artist, scenographer, light designer, props master and sound designer are members. Their respective functions in the theatre are capable of shaping human emotions and perceptions.

The effect and contribution of drama and theatre towards social change and nation building is best captured in Yerima's annoyance and understanding that society view itself from a position of the accused and demands social change. That drama can point towards social change, not effect social change itself (Yerima, 2013, p. 50). Drama and Theatre as collaborative arts depict a symbiotic relationship that exists between arts and the elements of theatre especially in the process of production planning. The collaboration shapes the performance into an appreciable piece of art that is relevant, topical and useful to the audience and society. The art of playwriting, directing, acting, stage management, design and arts administration put together by capable professionals of the theatre enhance the quality of performance placed before the audience. Each art requires a special craft and each craft plays significant roles in any production. For instance Jegede observes that:

A stage manager should be familiar with the requirements of the many personnel such as stagehands, actors, and musicians...a stage manager is an artist, a parent, a friend, a confidant, a nurse, a drill sergeant and a cheerleader. A good stage manager is a tactful communicator having a sense of humour. He realizes that the bulk of responsibility for the smooth running of the rehearsal process and the production is on his shoulders (2013, p. 23)

While the stage manager takes directions from the director, he or she reinforces the directions of the play director, re-checks the progress of work and activities with the actors and other arts as rehearsal progresses. Also the scenographer's job in the process of a production is as vital as any other because “it clarifies the mission and purpose of a theatrical performance” (Adegbite: 2010, p. 373), it vivifies the visual aspects of a production and, as Adegbite (2010: p. 374) says, provides

...details which are critical for the adoption of a dramatic masterpiece that is being perceived on stage. Thus, scenic design can then be singled out from this art (scenography)

to be the merger of all the tangible visual effects of the theatrical performance.

Both the artistic and the theatre design work within the spine of the play and the directorial concept of the director. That is why the props master is as important as the costume artist, the makeup artist, the scenographer, the light designer, the actors, the director, the playwright and the management team for the production. The collaboration aids the understanding of the performance, clarifies images and actions for the audience hence “all the arts of the theatre should be well harnessed and no art should be emphasized at the expense of another” (Ayodele: 2010, p. 369). However, developing a sustainable theatre practice in a security tasked, economically challenged, and terrorized country, such as Nigeria, requires the professional acumen of the arts of the theatre.

Synopsis of *Silhouettes*

Silhouettes (subtitled *Shadows from the Past*) written in 1993 is a play of ten incidents. It is a play that confronts the socio-cultural and political issues in Amadike, touching on universal issues ranging from leadership failure, propaganda, corruption and political campaign, to murder, incest and peace treaty. In this dramatic piece, Duruaku presents Obialor’s family as a traditional family sworn to guard the Kingship and traditional stool of the people of Amadike. At the death of the last king of Amadike his children prepare to elect a new king among the Princes. Nwaeze, prominent amongst the Princes, nudges Obialor to support him. But Obialor declares Nwaeze unqualified because there was a pact between the people of Amadike and the Apelle people. The said pact is captured in the *Silhouettes* thus “the child born of an Apelle Princess and the Eze of this clan shall rule the land. And that line shall produce the heirs. That is why our northern and eastern borders are safe. That is why we have not been exterminated by the Abobo cannibals” (p.17). Owing to this pact, even though Nwaeze is a Prince, he is not from the ‘Second line succession’. Nwaeze refuses to yield to that treaty made very many years ago by his forebears which excludes him and other Princes of non-Apelle affiliate from becoming king. Nwaeze demands for the abrogation of the peace treaty. He goes further to mobilize his men who threaten Obialor and his family, bribe the elders, poison Udoka and harass the elders of Amadike who refuse to agree with him. Nwaeze’s obsession leads him and his men into terrorizing Amadike community. Ironically his sins later find him out as one of his supporters, Maduka, discovers that it was Nwaeze who committed incest with Ugonna and got her pregnant but pushed the blame to Udoka. Ugonna is Maduka’s daughter. The Odejimjim youth summon Nwaeze before the elders and he is exiled.

Collaboration and Symbiosis in the Performance of *Silhouettes*

At the first production meeting, the director explained to all cast and crew her production concept of *Silhouettes* and how she intends to orchestrate it to fit into the Golden Jubilee Anniversary themed ‘Celebration’. That decision necessitated that the script will go through a script workshop. After a three-day workshop session with all cast and crew, the director emerged with a directorial concept- metaphorically “a dangling crown” and a presentational approach of which every cast and crew aligned with. After several readings, research and interactions with the cast and crew, the director’s reflections and inspiration

was drawn from the traditional elements in the play. The flashback scene in page eleven (11) of *Silhouettes* formed the background, the spine from which every other character and their actions were drawn from. In the flashback, the playwright captures the interaction and actions that gave birth to the present circumstances in Amadike as follows:

Eze Amadi: Let us wait a little longer, Dibia Ukama. I have faith in your position, but they have not helped my son these past days. The divination says he will die on the 40th day of his illness if a cure is not found. The Great One from Egwenga, the land of the four sacred rivers, is the only sure answer (p.11)

Ukama: Who is sure that such a being exists? Today is the thirtieth day and my new herbs need time to work my lord. (p.12)

Eze Amadi: Another problem. You say these new herbs will put him in deep sleep. Supposing he does not come out of that sleep. Supposing our messengers return with the answer. (p.12)

Ukama: If they return??

This scene is interpreted as an obligatory scene and retained with minor modifications.

In the world of the play, we see the expression of confidence in the traditional stool and what it stands for, but some skepticism of its efficacy in the present dispensation. Yet in times of crisis, the people find strength and answers in the treaty the ancestors made two hundred years ago. This researcher had explained this further elsewhere that “*Silhouettes*...is a tale of power tussle; a refracted construct that looks at sociopolitical ironies bedeviling the Nigerian political arena” (2013, p. 8). Thus, the confusion that Nwaeze wants to be king at all cost reminds the people that,

Amadi: The child born of an Apelle princess and the Eze of this Clan shall rule the land. And that line shall produce the heirs. That is why our northern and eastern borders are safe. That is why we have not been exterminated by the Abobo cannibals. (p.17)

Based on the peace treaty between Amadike and Apelle, bloodshed stopped, as Chidi explains that,

Chidi: It was agreed through a referendum that the Second line Succession would continue as long as it served its purpose. After six such marriages to Apelle

women, it was agreed by Amadike and Apelle that the Eze may no longer marry an Apelle maiden since Apelle blood was now running deep in the royal family. But the Apelle blood-line continues to produce the Eze in an election. (p.19)

Hence, Nwaeze, though a prince, is not qualified to vie for the Ezeship. The demand by Nwaeze for the abrogation of the peace treaty stirs up a conflict in the world of the play. The refusal by Obialor, Eke Igwe and other traditional custodians to yield to Nwaeze's demand infuriates him. But this "singular interest of Nwaeze to rule Amadike irrespective of the fact that Nwaeze is not from the 'Second line succession', unearths a can of worms- murder, incest, terror and greed- which is what Nigerians witness in every campaign year" (Ogbonna, 2013, p. 8). However, the peace treaty in the world of the play can be compared to the Nigerian zoning system in the political climate and the question is- has it been effective? To restore confidence in the traditional institution, the performance under review heightened the character of Obialor and his insistence on keeping to the treaty till it won at the end.

Also Nwaeze's determination to become Eze at all cost shows the kind of leader he will become as we hear him (Nwaeze) promise a recalcitrant Obialor in this dialogue,

Nwaeze: We shall have a smooth coronation. In my cabinet, you will occupy a place of honour. Be rest assured that I shall reward you (p. 4)

Obialor: ...Things must be done properly. If you are sure of being unanimously chosen, why don't you call for a referendum? Yes! If the people want the old ways changed, then you may seek nomination for the throne. That is the only way you can qualify...look at what is happening in Mbazuruka. They cast away the rules and now the community has been torn apart like an old rag (p.4)

Nwaeze:...Mbazuruka is a town of no consequence.

It is evident that Nwaeze's determination to become the Eze of Amadike is out of greed and selfishness which accounts for the monies shared by his campaign managers in order to convince certain elders in his favour. That is why the character of Chidi bemoans that:

Chidi: A society where poverty has taken the front seat has little moral values. A contented man is hard to bribe. Crimes increase with poor economy (p.9).

In this performance, the opposition given to Nwaeze, Maduka, Maduiké, Obidike and their men by the custodians of the people's culture and tradition shows that Amadike is resilient and anchors on their traditional platform. The images in *Silhouettes* are not uncommon in the Nigerian society, rather it is how effectively the director and her collaborators arranged and channelled the visual images and idioms of the play into concrete life-like actions that made the difference. Opposition given to Nwaeze, Maduka, Maduiké, Obidike and their men by the custodians of the people's culture and tradition shows that Amadike is resilient and anchors on their traditional platform. The images in *Silhouettes* are not uncommon in the Nigerian society, rather it is how effective the director and her collaborators have arranged and channelled the visual images and idioms of the play into concrete life-like actions that made the difference.

After analysis of the play, the director chose a "dangling crown" as the most suitable directorial concept. And for her directorial approach she chose the presentational approach which Kpodoh described thus "presentational is the theory and practice of drama as frankly theatrical and fictional presentation" (2006, p. 29). With these the performance was able to point towards mass social action. Her metaphor that loomed large was hung centre stage from the beginning to the end of the performance and also reflected majorly in the acting. Also to get the best out of the play, the director became auteur directorially and added three scenes that complement the script. The first (Incident 1), was a scene where the entire village danced at the village square to declare the Ezeship seat vacant and ready for a new Eze. The second (Incident Seven) brought Ugonna on stage to visit Chidi. The third (Incident Eleven) which ends the play is also a new scene created to take place at the Village square where the Odejimjim, the youths summon Nwaeze and the custodians exiled him. The techniques of freezes, elevation and posture were applied to these newly created scenes to give them prominence, emphasis and stability. Spectacular dances were incorporated to moderate intermissions.

The set/scenography played very important role in this performance as it aided the portrayal of the concept of the play. The 'dangling crown' was placed along the bush path (Centre Stage) that separates Obialor's house from Nwaeze's- the same path where Udoka's dead body was found. Again, while the visual representations of the locales were presentational, the flashback was represented with tree stumps as seats, bush paths, and a mixture of colours to reflect ancient times; the costumes and makeup created historical classification of the characters. Simultaneous staging was used with intent to express a close-knit-village setting. Obialor's house was stage left; Nwaeze's stage right; the bush path was played at the orchestra pitch linking another bush centre stage. Then atop of a tree was the 'dangling crown'. The seats at Obialor's house were tree stumps painted earth colour; those used at Nwaeze's house are painted differently; and Nwaeze's seats are painted with bright colours to depict affluence, flamboyance and a touch of modern/Western contact. Obialor's house remains traditional from the seats to the walls and the accessories as well as traditional mantle. However, some original scenes that preempted

the actions of the play were removed and some characters killed and recreated in order to create suspense.

However, major challenges were encountered in this production from the cast and crew because the director's colleagues formed eighty percent of the cast and crew, hence much time was expended at rehearsals. But it was a refreshing experience because the director learnt new skills especially in the area of human relations.

Conclusion

Directing in the theatre is a team work which brings together all the arts of the theatre for a unified production. It is an art that harmonizes other arts in the theatre. Its synthesizing function mobilizes other arts into a creative and collaborative enterprise. Hence the success of any production depends immensely "on hard work, commitment, sacrifice, endurance and dedication by the artistic director and his collaborators" (Bell-Gam: 2007, p. 86). As the professional personnel in the theatre whose function goes beyond the mere movement of actors and furniture on stage, the director is conscious of the environment for which the play is being produced, and the expected effect the performance is to have on the audience. Another step that ensures quality in a production is the director's ability to harmonize the other arts by making sure that their creativity aligns to the concept of the production. Again, a good director must not necessarily be a Gordon Craig adherent, a disciple of Laissez faire or a Via Media freak but one who relates with people humanely as issues emerge. The performance of *Silhouettes* under review here was "an expose on the past, the present and what future..." (Ogbonna: 2013, p. 8). It captured to a large extent the socio-political and economic realities of the contemporary Nigerian scene. Thus, in any performance, systematic collaboration with other arts of the theatre ensures quality, effectiveness and achievement of set objectives. The researcher concludes that themed productions are veritable tools in the re-enforcement and effective communication of the playwright's message as interpreted by the director and her/his crew.

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